

THE STATE AS THE MAIN SUBJECT OF INTRODUCTION OF
GREEN ECONOMY IN THE REGIONS

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Abstract: *In this article, the preservation of nature, improvement of ecological status, green economy, provision of green economic growth and preservation of resources necessary for human life and health, environment and ecology as a whole, a new direction of economic activity based on the implementation of further development of the economy related to the production and service sectors and "green" investments of the State.*

Keywords: *nature, ecological condition, green economy, investment, resources, environment, economic activity.*

State "green" investments

The government plays a crucial role in increasing public investment and mobilizing innovative financial instruments for the "green" transition. In 2021, Uzbekistan issued bonds in the amount of 870 million US dollars to finance activities to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). These goals include, inter alia, land restoration, development of "green" transport, launching of the "Green Sukuk" mechanism, financing of energy efficiency improvement projects and other innovations (Ministry of Finance). However, according to the new development strategy for 2022-2026, these activities, which require additional funds, are not enough for a "green" transition. International experience shows that countries should be able to mobilize financial resources in the amount of 6% of the

gross domestic product (GDP) to achieve the goals of the Paris Agreement. It is important to attract both public and private investment and reduce the risk of climate change for previously planned investments. According to the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 30, 2021 No. 73 on the state budget for 2022, the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the support of international development partners (UNDP and the French Development Agency (FTA)) It is the leading state body for "green" financial reform in order to implement the "green" transition.

Current work includes the development of a "green" budgeting methodology, linking public expenditures with BRM and regular monitoring, introducing the principles of "green" and sustainable public procurement, and reforms in the field of "greening" the tax and subsidy system. At the same time, the Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan contributes to the creation of a favorable environment for "green" investments through the "Green" investment council¹.

State investments. International experience has shown that the coordination of financial policy frameworks with climate change mitigation and emission reduction goals involves various reforms, as an example, we can mention the integration of environmental goals with budget financing and tax policy reform. In Uzbekistan, 10% of GDP goes to subsidies for energy resources: a review of this sector would help encourage the use of clean energy sources and rational use of natural resources. The investment needed to decarbonize the electric power sector in Uzbekistan by 2030 is estimated at 4 billion US dollars per year or 4.8% of GDP (Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan). Thus, the revision of financial policy and subsidies, as well as the introduction of a "green" public procurement model will help accelerate the "green" transition.

Consider the carbon tax system used in many countries to reduce emissions.

Private investments. Advanced international experience shows that in order

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to attract the private sector, appropriate regulatory structures, tools and incentives should be created in the country. A good starting point is to develop green finance roadmaps based on best practice examples from the UK, Indonesia and South Africa.

In the case of Uzbekistan, the "greening" of the banking sector plays an important role with the possibility of developing a "Green" taxonomy. This helps to create a database for the investor, for example, how the country provides information about its impact on the economy and social development, investing pension funds in "green" projects. on pension fund activities and others².

Based on the above points, the following conclusion can be reached: the transition to the "green" economy requires large investments, so the state budget alone is not enough. Active involvement of private investors in low-carbon technologies is necessary. That is,

1. Uzbekistan is taking steps towards a "green" transition, which can be complemented by the introduction of innovative fiscal tools. Economic modeling of carbon and fuel taxes can help governments better define incentives for the wider adoption of clean energy and clean fuels; and is consistent with the distributional aspects of "green" fiscal reform. Expanding green public procurement is another policy tool to encourage green investment.

2. It is very important to increase the possibility of international climate financing. Access to the Green Climate Fund (GCF) can be achieved by accrediting entities as "Implementing Agencies". The banking sector requires additional training and capacity building to obtain YIJ accreditation and to successfully prepare and submit project proposals to YIJ.

1. Green legislation, green infrastructure planning, budgeting, and use of relevant regulatory bodies, tools, and capacity building are necessary to attract the private sector to green financing and investment.

2. It is necessary to create a results monitoring system to evaluate the

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effectiveness of "green" investments. International experience and the guidelines of the World Bank can help Uzbekistan to introduce a modern "green" taxonomy, including the formation of the framework for the scope, guidelines and criteria of "green" investments and "green" purchases.

3. Green investment opportunities require cooperation between public and private actors to connect investors and potential investments, both locally and internationally. Local companies know where to invest, while international companies are looking for investment opportunities. The development of cooperation between them will become a common interest.

4. Raising awareness about "green" loans and "green" banking products, as well as disseminating information about the impact of climate change and the importance and importance of climate change among local entrepreneurs, helping to increase their interest in the topic gives

Implementation of the tasks defined in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the effectiveness of the measures implemented to ensure "green" and inclusive economic growth within the framework of the strategy of the transition to the "green" economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. A number of decrees and decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan were issued in order to increase the use of renewable energy sources and further expand the saving of resources in all sectors of the economy. In particular:

In accordance with Appendix 1, the program for the transition to a "green" economy and ensuring "green" growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, which is intended to achieve the following strategic goals:

a) reduction of greenhouse gas emissions per unit of GDP by 35% from the level of 2010;

b) increase the production capacity of renewable energy sources by 15 GW and increase their share to more than 30% of the total volume of electricity production;

c) increase energy efficiency in industry by at least 20%;

d) reduce the amount of energy consumption per unit of gross domestic product by 30%, including by expanding the use of renewable energy sources;

i) to significantly increase the efficiency of water use in all sectors of the economy, to introduce water-saving irrigation technology on an area of up to 1 million hectares;

f) by planting 200 million saplings per year and increasing the total number of saplings from 1 billion, expanding green areas in cities by more than 30 percent;

j) increase the index of reserves of the forest fund of the republic to more than 90 million cubic meters;

h) to increase the level of processing of generated solid household waste from 65 percent;

2) The concept of transition to a "green" economy and ensuring energy efficiency in industrial sectors,

3) Uzbe until 2030

an action plan for the transition to a "green" economy and ensuring "green" growth in the Republic of Kazakhstan,

4) Target parameters for saving fuel and energy resources in economic sectors in 2022-2026 aimed at reducing the energy capacity of products produced in 25 enterprises and organizations by 20% by 2026 compared to 2022.

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